

Analysis of factors influencing work accidents among Bajo Tribe Fishermen in the Coastal Area of Nelayan Bhakti Village, South Wangi-Wangi District, Wakatobi Regency 2023

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Abstract

Background: Occupational Safety and Health (OSH) is an inseparable part of the employment and human resources system. To increase fishermen's productivity, it is very necessary to implement Occupational Safety and Health (K3). The aim of this research is to analyze the factors that influence work accidents among Bajo fishermen in the coastal area of the Nelayan Bhakti village, South Wangi-Wangi subdistrict, Wakatobi Regency.

Method: This research uses a quantitative analytical approach method design studies cut latitude (cross sectional). The population in this study were all fishermen from the Bajo tribe in the Nelayan Bhakti Village, Wangi-Wangi Selatan District, Wakatobi Regency, totaling 470 people who worked as fishermen. The number of samples in this study was 212 who worked as fishermen. The results of this research show the influence of knowledge on work accidents with the results of the chi-square test analysis with a value of $p= 0.000$, attitude with a value of $p= 0.000$, use of personal protective equipment with a value of $p= 0.000$, machine condition with a value of $p= 0.000$ and machine safety equipment with a value of $p= 0.000$. The conclusion of this research is that knowledge, attitudes, personal protective equipment, machine conditions and machine safety equipment have a significant influence on work accidents among Bajo fishermen.

Results: The results of this study show the influence of knowledge on work accidents with the results of the chi-square test analysis with a value of $p= 0.000$, attitude with a value of $p= 0.000$, use of personal protective equipment with a value of $p= 0.000$, machine condition with a value of $p= 0.000$ and machine safety equipment with a value of $p= 0.000$. The conclusion of this research is that knowledge, attitudes, personal protective equipment, machine conditions and machine safety equipment have a significant influence on work accidents among Bajo fishermen.

Conclusion: The conclusion of this research is that knowledge, attitudes, personal protective equipment, machine condition and machine safety equipment have a significant influence on work accidents among Bajo fishermen.

Keywords: Work Accident; Fishermen; Coastal area

1. Introduction

Country like Indonesia is areas that are included There are 8,090 coastal zones in Indonesia which spreads across 300 districts and 67.87 million people. Of 234.2 million people The population in Indonesia is informal sector workers as

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many as 30% of fishermen are one of many from sectors that are currently developing in the fishing industry in Indonesia [1].

The Bajo tribe in Indonesia is a community of people who live along coastal areas throughout the archipelago, almost 95% of whom work as fishermen and face many threats when carrying out fishing activities to meet their daily needs. [2]. The implementation of K3 aspects should not only focus on formal industry, but also on informal industry/sector, because the informal sector itself has the same elements as the formal sector, namely that there are workers, tools and work environments that interact with each other. There is also a need for education by informal workers to improve safety at work [3]. To increase fishermen's productivity, it is very necessary to implement Occupational Safety and Health (K3), which is related to Law no. 1 of 1970 concerning Work Safety and in ILO Convention no. 155 of 1980 concerning Occupational Safety and Health (K3) [4].

Based on data from the International *Labor Organization* (ILO), it is stated that almost every day people die due to work accidents or work-related diseases, more than 2.78 million people die per year, of which 2.4 million workers (86.3%) die due to work-related diseases and 380,000 workers (13.7%) died due to work-related diseases, it is estimated that globally lost working days are equivalent to 4% of Global Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and even in some places 6% [5]. Analysis from the *Center for Occupational Occupation Injury* (CFOI) conducted by the BLS (Bureau of Labor Statistics) in 2002 stated that the risk of occupational accidents for fishermen was 20 – 30 times compared to other types of work. The general risks are that almost all of the work equipment is not equipped with self-saving equipment, low levels of education, and also the large risks borne due to lack of knowledge and attitudes that underestimate work which are the triggers for work accidents that occur [6].

The initial survey was conducted on October 11 2023. The total population of Mola Nelayan Bhakti Village was 2,210 people with 1,091 men and 1,119 women. It is recorded in the village profile that the livelihood of the population is 470 fishermen, and the population who do not work is 425 people. Tonda fishing boats are a type of fishing boat that is dominantly used by Bajo Tribe fishermen in Bhakti Fisherman Village on South Wangi-Wangi Island. The type of trolling boat used by fishermen is a motorboat or what local people call a rod body with a size of <5 GT. Data on the number of work accidents at the South Wangi-Wangi Health Service (Wakatobi Health Office 2023) in 2021-2023 showed that there were 185 fishermen in the Bhakti fishing village who experienced work accidents. Work accidents that often occur among Bajo fishermen in the Bhakti fishing village include falls, sprains, broken bones and other work accidents.

2. Material and methods

This research method uses a quantitative analytical approach design studies cut latitude (*cross sectional*) because study This takes place at the same time for the dependent variable and the independent variable. The aim of this quantitative research is to analyze the factors that influence work accidents among Bajo tribe fishermen in the coastal area of Bhakti Fisherman Village, South Wangi-Wangi District, Wakatobi Regency. The population in this study were 470 fishermen from the Bajo tribe in the Nelayan Bhakti Village, Wangi-Wangi Selatan District, Wakatobi Regency, who worked as fishermen. The number of samples was determined using the *Lemeshow formula*. Based on the *Lemeshow* formula, the sample size was 212 respondents.

Technique taking sample on research This that is purposive *sampling* is sampling based on certain considerations. Criteria inclusion is terms subject Which will researched And can made research representative. Criteria inclusion in this study were fishermen from the Bajo tribe who had a work accident in December 2023. Meanwhile, the exclusion criteria in the research were Bajo tribe fishermen who had never experienced a work accident in December 2023. The independent variables *in* this study were work experience, knowledge, attitudes, personal protective equipment, machine condition, and machine safety equipment. The *dependent* variable is work accidents.

Data collection techniques Data primary obtained with technique collection data Which in a way direct in field by researcher. Data primary Also called as data original or data new, taken use technique collection the data from questionnaires and direct interviews on the source during activity study. As for source Those selected were respondents whose livelihood is as a fisherman in Coastal Area of the Bajo Tribe, Fisherman Bhakti Village, Wangi-Wangi Selatan District, Wakatobi Regency.

Meanwhile, secondary data is obtained or collected from existing sources previously. Secondary data is data obtained from agencies provider data Which relate that is from information related on accident Work Which obtained through the media internet, articles science etc. The research instruments used were questionnaire sheets, writing tools, a camera as a documentation tool and SPSS.

The data obtained were analyzed statistically using univariate, bivariate and multivariate analysis. The results of univariate analysis aim to explain the characteristics of respondents using categorical data. Bivariate analysis in this study used the chi square test and multivariate analysis used the binary logistic regression test with a confidence level of 95% to determine the most dominant factors influencing work accidents among fishermen.

3. Research result

3.1. Respondent Characteristics

3.1.1. Univariate Analysis

Table 1 Frequency distribution based on age group, gender, length of work of Bajo ethnic fishermen in the coastal area of Bhakti fishing village, Wangi-Wangi Selatan sub-district, Wakatobi Regency 2023

Age	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
> 40 Years	104	49.1
< 40 Years	108	50.9
Total	212	100
Gender		
Man	212	100
Total	212	100
Years of service		
> 5 Years	122	71.7
< 5 Years	90	28.3
Total	212	100
Education		
elementary school	86	40.6
Junior high school	81	38.2
Senior high school	36	17.0
S1	9	4.2
Total	212	100

Source: (Primary Data, 2023)

Based on Table 1, it shows that of the 212 respondents, it is known that the percentage of fishermen in the age group > 40 years is 104 respondents (49.1%), while fishermen in the age group < 40 years are 108 (50.9%). Meanwhile, 212 respondents (100%) were male. Respondents with > years of service were 122 (71.7%) respondents with < 5 years were 90 (28.3%). Meanwhile, 86 respondents (40.6%) had elementary school education, 81 (38.2%) had junior high school, 36 (17.0%) had high school and 9 respondents (4.2%) had bachelor's degrees.

Based on table 2, the frequency distribution shows that the number of work accidents for fishermen is 44 (20.8%) who have experienced work accidents, while there are 168 (79.2%) fishermen who have never experienced work accidents. The types of work accidents that often occur among fishermen are slips, 79 (37.3%), injuries, 61 (28.8%), sprains, 27 (12.7%) and 45 respondents (21.2%) who fell into the sea. Meanwhile, the parts of the body that are often injured due to fishing work accidents are most often found in the feet, 99 (47.7%), hands, 84 (39.6%), neck, 14 (6.6%) and the head, 15 (7.1%).

Table 2 Frequency distribution based on work accidents, types of work accidents experienced, parts of the body affected by work accidents by Bajo tribal fishermen in the coastal area of the Bhakti fishing village, South Wangi-Wangi sub-district, Wakatobi Regency

Work accident	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
There has been a work accident	44	20.8
Never Had an Accident	168	79.2
Total	212	100
Types of Accidents		
slip	79	37.3
Wound	61	28.8
sprain	27	12.7
Falling overboard	45	21.2
Total	212	100
Body Parts Suffering from Work Accidents		
Head	15	7.1
Neck	14	6.6
Hand	84	39.6
Foot	99	46.7
Total	212	100

Source: (Primary Data, 2023)

Table 3 Frequency distribution based on knowledge, attitudes, use of protective equipment in Bajo tribal fishermen in the coastal area of Bhakti fishing village, Wangi-Wangi Selatan sub-district, Wakatobi Regency

Knowledge	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
Good	153	72.2
Not good	59	27.8
Total	212	100
Attitude		
Good	155	73.1
Not good	57	26.9
Total	212	100
Personal protective equipment		
Complete	148	69.8
Incomplete	64	30.2
Total	212	100

Source: (Primary Data, 2023)

The frequency of good fishing knowledge was 153 (72.2%). Meanwhile, fishermen with poor knowledge were 59 (27.8%). Good fishermen attitude was 155 (73.1%). Meanwhile, 57 respondents (26.9%) had poor fishermen attitudes. Meanwhile, there were 148 fishermen (69.8%) who had protective equipment (PPE), while 64 respondents (30.2%) did not have personal protective equipment (PPE).

Table 4 Frequency distribution based on the condition of machines and machine safety equipment for Bajo tribal fishermen in the coastal area of the Bhakti fishing village, Wangi-Wangi Selatan sub-district, Wakatobi Regency

Machine Condition	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
Works fine	154	72.6
Not functioning properly	58	27.4
Total	212	100
Machine Safety Devices		
There is security	152	71.7
There is no security	60	28.3
Total	212	100

Source: (Primary Data, 2023)

Based on table 4, it shows the frequency distribution of the condition of fishermen's machines. Of the 212 respondents, fishermen whose engines functioned well were 154 (72.6%) while fishermen whose engines did not function well were 58 respondents (27.4%). Meanwhile, there were 152 respondents (71.7%) who had machine guards, while there were 60 respondents (28.3%) who did not have machine guards.

3.1.2. Bivariate Analysis

An analysis carried out to see the relationship between several influencing factors on work accidents of fishermen from the Bajo tribe in the coastal area of the Bhakti fishing village, Wangi-Wangi Selatan sub-district, Wakatobi Regency. Following is connection a number of factor on accidentin Work which can be seen in table 5:

Table 5 The relationship between work experience and work accidents among Bajo fishermen in the coastal area of the Bhakti fishing village, Wangi-wangi Selatan sub-district, Wakatobi district

Years of service	Work accident				Total		P-Value
	Once Work Accident Occurs		Never Occurred Work Accidents		n	%	
	n	%	n	%			
> 5 Years	22	10.4	100	47.2	122	57.5	0.167
< 5 Years	22	10.4	68	32.1	90	42.5	
Total	44	20.8	168	79.3	212	100	
Knowledge							
Good	4	1.9	149	70.3	153	72.2	0,000
Not good	40	18.9	19	9.0	59	27.8	
Total	44	20.8	168	79.3	212	100	
Attitude							
Good	5	2,4	150	70.8	155	73.1	0,000
Not good	39	18.4	18	8.5	57	26.9	
Total	44	20.8	168	79.3	212	100	
Personal protective equipment							
Complete	4	1.9	144	67.9	148	69.8	0,000
Incomplete	44	18.9	24	11.3	64	30.2	

Total	44	20.8	168	79.2	212	100	
Machine Condition							
Works fine	3	1.4	151	72.2	154	72.6	0,000
Not functioning properly	41	19.3	17	8.9	58	27.4	
Total	44	20.8	168	79.3	212	100	
Machine Safety Devices							
There is a machine guard	6	2.8	146	68.9	152	71.1	0,000
No Engine Guard	38	17.9	22	10.4	60	28.3	
Total	44	20.8	168	79.3	212	100	

Source: (Primary Data, 2023)

Based on table 5, the research results show that fishermen with period Work >5 year experience accident Work as much 22 (10.4%) And fisherman Those who did not experience work accidents were 100 (47.2%). I research too obtained fisherman with period Work <5 year experience accident Work as much 22 (10.4%) And fisherman Which No experience accident Work as much 68 (32.1%) However, on results test statistics No there is connection period Work to incident accident Work with mark $p = 0.167 < \alpha (0.05)$

In the knowledge variable, the research results show that good knowledge is obtained accident in Work as big as 4 (1.9%) as well as Which No 149 (70.3%) had accidents at work. Research results too It was found that fishermen with poor knowledge had accidents worked by 40 (18.9%) as well as fishermen who did not have accidents in Work amounted to 19 (9.0%). The results of statistical tests using *chi-square* obtained a p value = 0.000. Because the p value $< \alpha (0.05)$ means that there is a relationship between knowledge and work accidents.

The attitude variable shows that fishermen with good attitudes gain accident in Work as big as 5 (2.4%) as well as Which No 150 (70.8%) had accidents at work. The results of this research too found fishermen with less good attitudes worked by 39 (18.4%) and fishermen who did not have accidents in Work amounted to 18 (8.5%). The results of statistical tests using *chi-square* obtained a p value = 0.000. Because the p value $< \alpha (0.05)$ means that there is a relationship between knowledge and work accidents among fishermen.

Meanwhile, regarding the personal protective equipment variable, the research results show that fishermen who have personal protective equipment get it accident in Work as big as 4 (2.4%) as well as Which No 144 (67.9%) had accidents at work. The results of this research too It was found that fishermen without personal protective equipment were involved in accidents worked by 40 (18.9%) as well as fishermen who did not have accidents in Work amounted to 24 (11.3%). The results of statistical tests using *chi-square* obtained a p value = 0.000. Because the p value $< \alpha (0.05)$ means that there is a relationship between personal protective equipment and work accidents among Bajo tribal fishermen in the coastal area of the Bhakti fishing village, South Wangi-Wangi subdistrict, Wakatobi Regency.

Meanwhile, for the machine condition variable, the research shows that fishermen with good functioning machine conditions get results accident in Work as big as 3 (1.4%) as well as Which No There were 151 accidents at work (71.2%). The results of this research too It was found that fishermen whose machines were not functioning properly had accidents worked by 41 (19.3%) and fishermen who did not have accidents in Work amounted to 17 (8.0%). The results of statistical tests using *chi-square* obtained a p value = 0.000. Because the p value $< \alpha (0.05)$ means that there is a relationship between machine conditions and work accidents among fishermen.

The variable safety device on the machine, research results show that fishing with machine safety has occurred accident in Work as big as 6 (2.8%) and fishermen have engine guards No There were 146 accidents at work (68.9%). The results of this research too It was found that fishermen whose engines did not have safety guards had experienced accidents worked by 38 (17.9%) and fishermen who did not have accidents in Work amounted to 22 (10.4%). The results of statistical tests using *chi-square* obtained a p value = 0.000. Because the p value $< \alpha (0.05)$ means that there is a relationship between machine safety equipment and work accidents among fishermen.

3.1.3. Multivariate Analysis

Analysis Multivariate aim For test Multivariate aim Fornow variable where Which most dominant influence affecting fishermen's work accidents in Nelayan Bhakti Village, Wangi-Wangi Selatan District, Wakatobi Regency.

Table 6 Selection of Variables to Become Candidate Models in *Logistic Regression Tests* Based on Bivariate Analysis

Variable	p-Value	Information
Knowledge	0,000	Candidate
Attitude	0,000	Candidate
Personal protective equipment	0,000	Candidate
Machine Condition	0,000	Candidate
Machine Safety Devices	0,000	Candidate

Based on Table 6, it is known that the variables are test candidates binary logistic regression, namely the variables of knowledge, attitude, personal protective equipment, machine safety conditions.

Table 7 Binary Logistic Regression Test Results

Variable	B	Sig.	OR	95% CI
Knowledge	-1,622	0.050	0.198	0.039- 0.999
Attitude	-1,458	0.049	0.233	0.054-0.996
Protective Equipment Dir	-1,417	0.082	0.242	0.049-1.195
Machine Condition	-1,926	0.045	0.146	0.022-0.962
Machine Safety Devices	-.211	0.083	0.810	0.0107- 6.158

Based on Table 7 from the multivariate results using binary logistic regression, 3 variables were obtained that influence the incidence of work accidents among fishermen, namely:

- The risk factor for work accidents that has the dominant influence is the machine condition variable with a p value <0.040, OR of 0.146 (95% CI 0.022-0.962). Fishermen who have poor knowledge have an accident risk that is 0.146 times greater than fishermen who have good knowledge.
- The most dominant risk factor for work accidents is the attitude variable with a p value <0.049, OR of 0.233 (95% CI 0.054-0.996). Fishermen with poor attitudes have a 0.233 greater risk of having work accidents than fishermen with good attitudes.
- The last most dominant risk factor for work accidents is the machine condition variable with a p value <0.049, OR of 0.146 (95% CI 0.022-0.962). Fishermen with machines that are not functioning properly are at 0.146 greater risk of having work accidents than fishermen with machines that are functioning well.

4. Discussion

4.1. The Effect of Working Period on Fishermen's Work Accidents

Based on the research results, it shows that fishermen with mass Work >5 year experience accident Work as much 22 (10.4%) And fisherman Which No experience accident Work as much 100 (47.2%). Results study Also obtained fisherman with period Work <5 year experience accident Work as much 22 (10.4%) And fisherman Which No experience accident Work as much 68 (32.1%) in Fisherman Bhakti Village, Wangi-Wangi Selatan District, Wakatobi Regency.

However, on results test statistics No there isconnection period Work to incident accident Work with mark $p = 0.167$. This research is in line with research by E. Egriana Handayani, Trisno AgungWibowo And Dyah Syriac (2020) in PT borneo transverse buana export Yogyakarta, that in a way statistics No There is connection Which significant between periodwork on accident incident Work with mark $p = 0.813$.

The International Labor Organization (1989) stated that it is a matter of time Work is a key factor causing work accidents but it must also be remembered that many period Work No automatic can show happen accident Work.

4.2. The Effect of Knowledge on Work Accidents in Fishermen

One's knowledge is very important in shaping one's actions. Lack of knowledge about occupational safety and health will lead to unsafe actions that can result in work accidents. In accordance with the results of direct observations in the field, there are still some fishermen with poor knowledge of safety at work, such as the use of personal protective equipment (PPE), the use of safety equipment on machines, an attitude of not caring about dangerous conditions when working, carrying out work and not paying attention to the condition of the machine used when carrying out the work. Poor knowledge can cause work accidents.

Based on the research results, it shows that fishermen with good knowledge experience accident Work as much 22 (10.4%) And fisherman Which No experience accident Work as much 100 (47.2%). Results study Also obtained fisherman with poor knowledge experienced accident Work as much 22 (10.4%) And fisherman Which No experience accident Work as much 68 (32.1%) in Fisherman Bhakti Village, Wangi-Wangi Selatan District, Wakatobi Regency. The results of the *chi-square* statistical test showed a *p-value* = 0.000 ($p < 0.05$), can concluded that There is connection knowledge with accident Work on Tribal Fishermen in Fisherman Bhakti Village, Wangi-Wangi Selatan District, Wakatobi Regency.

4.3. The Influence of Attitudes on Fishermen's Work Accidents

The research results show that fishermen with a good attitude earn accident in Work as big as 5 (2.4%) as well as Which No 150 (70.8%) had accidents at work. The results of this research too It was found that fishermen with poor attitudes had accidents worked by 39 (18.4%) and fishermen who did not have accidents in Work amounted to 18 (8.5%). in Bhakti Fisherman Village, South Wangi-Wangi District, Wakatobi Regency. The results of the *chi-square* statistical test showed a *p-value* = 0.000 ($p < 0.05$), can concluded that There is attitude relationship with accident Work on Tribal Fishermen in Fisherman Bhakti Village, Wangi-Wangi Selatan District, Wakatobi Regency .

4.4. The Effect of Personal Protective Equipment on Fishermen's Work Accidents

The research results show that fishermen who have personal protective equipment get it accident in Work as big as 4 (2.4%) as well as Which No 144 (67.9%) had accidents at work. The results of this research too It was found that fishermen without personal protective equipment were involved in accidents worked by 40 (18.9%) as well as fishermen who did not have accidents in Work amounted to 24 (11.3%). The results of statistical tests using *chi-square* obtained a *p-value* = 0.000. Because the *p-value* $< \alpha$ (0.05) means that there is an influence of personal protective equipment on work accidents among Bajo ethnic fishermen in the coastal area of the Bhakti fishing village, South Wangi-Wangi subdistrict, Wakatobi Regency.

Results study This in line with study Rahma Listyandini And TjiptoSuwandi (2019) at the NPK fertilizer factory there is a significant relationship between between protective equipment to incident accident Work with mark $p = 0.003$. The use of personal protective equipment is something that needs to be considered in controlling hazards. PPE functions for every worker to reduce the risk of dangerous impacts. Because it only reduces, it is necessary to avoid dependence on relying solely on personal protective equipment to complete each job.

4.5. Fishermen's Work Accidents

The results of the research show that fishing with engine safety has occurred accident in Work as big as 6 (2.8%) and fishermen have engine guards No There were 146 accidents at work (68.9%). The results of this research too It was found that fishermen whose engines did not have safety guards had experienced accidents worked by 38 (17.9%) and fishermen who did not have accidents in Work amounted to 22 (10.4%).

The results of statistical tests using *chi-square* obtained a *p-value* = 0.000. Because the *p-value* $< \alpha$ (0.05) means that there is a relationship between machine safety equipment and work accidents among Bajo tribal fishermen in the coastal area of the Bhakti fishing village, South Wangi-Wangi subdistrict, Wakatobi Regency. Equipment factors significantly influence work accidents $p = 0.024 < (\alpha = 0.05)$, risk accident Work on fisherman with equipment No safe 3 time more big compared to with equipment safe (OR=2.562 95%CI 1,121-5,858).

Equipment is items in the form of machines used by fishermen on a ship/boat for the fishing process or to complete a job so that it runs well. Equipment in the form of machines can cause this to happen accident Work fisherman If No

availability tool safety machine, so with The effort made is to add safety to the machine form fence wire or the like Which aim For minimize its occurrence accident on while working.

4.6. The Influence of Machine Conditions on Fishermen's Work Accidents

The results of the research show that fishermen with well-functioning machines earn accident in Work as big as 3 (1.4%) as well as Which No There were 151 accidents at work (71.2%). The results of this research too It was found that fishermen whose machines were not functioning properly had accidents worked by 41 (19.3%) and fishermen who did not have accidents in Work amounted to 17 (8.0%). The results of statistical tests using *chi-square* obtained a *p value* = 0.000. Because the *p value* < α (0.05) means that there is a relationship between machine condition and work accidents among Bajo fishermen in the coastal area of the Bhakti fishing village, South Wangi-Wangi subdistrict, Wakatobi Regency.

This research is in line with research conducted by Raja (2020). The results of the *Chi-Square test* show There is a significant relationship between machine conditions and work accidents (*Pvalue* = 0.011).

The condition of the machine can be classified as one of the factors causing work accidents. For prevent happen accident Work is with do routine maintenance by checking the condition of the machine before use so that opportunity For work accident reduce And capable incident avoided if the machine is in good functioning condition [7] . Problems that occur for fishermen when fishing in the middle of the ocean, such as a problematic boat engine or a flashlight that won't turn on.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of the research that has been carried out, it can be concluded that the factors influencing work accidents among Bajo Tribe Fishermen in Nelayan Bhakti Village, Wangi-Wangi Selatan District, Wakatobi Regency 2023:

- There is an influence of knowledge on work accidents among Bajo Tribe Fishermen in Nelayan Bhakti Village, Wangi-Wangi Selatan District, Wakatobi Regency 2023. The results of statistical tests using *chi-square* obtained a *p value* = 0.000 because the *p value* < α (0.05).
- There is an influence of attitude on work accidents among Bajo Tribe Fishermen in Nelayan Bhakti Village, Wangi-Wangi Selatan District, Wakatobi Regency 2023. The results of statistical tests using *chi-square* obtained a *p value* = 0.000 because the *p value* < α (0.05).
- There is an influence of the use of personal protective equipment on work accidents among Bajo Tribe Fishermen in Nelayan Bhakti Village, Wangi-Wangi Selatan District, Wakatobi Regency 2023. The results of statistical tests using *chi-square* obtained a *p value* = 0.000.
- There is an influence of machine conditions on work accidents among Bajo Tribal Fishermen in the Bhakti Fisherman Village, District Wangi-Wangi Selatan Wakatobi Regency 2023 The results of statistical tests using *chi-square* obtained a *p value* = 0.000 because the *p value* < α (0.05).
- There is an influence of machine safety equipment on work accidents among Bajo Tribal Fishermen in Nelayan Bhakti Village, Wangi-Wangi Selatan District, Wakatobi Regency in 2023. The *p value* = 0.000 is obtained because the *p value* < α (0.05)
- There is no influence of work experience on work accidents among Bajo Tribe Fishermen in Nelayan Bhakti Village, Wangi-Wangi Selatan District, Wakatobi Regency in 2023. The *p value* = 0.167 is obtained because the *p value* < α (0.05)

Suggestion

- The South Wangi-Wangi Health Service, Wakatobi Regency, created a health and safety program for workers, especially non-formal ones such as fishermen.
- Fishermen should pay more attention to their health and work safety by complying with all the requirements for being able to sail to avoid work accidents.
- Future researchers are advised to further develop this research topic in terms of other factors outside the variables that the researcher studied.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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